

Main functions of marketing and marketing strategy in agriculture of Uzbekistan until 2030

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The marketing function in agriculture covers a wide range of activities aimed at promoting and selling agricultural products. It includes the following aspects:

Market research: Market research helps identify market needs, analyze competitors, understand consumer preferences, and determine demand for specific agricultural products.

Product development: Agricultural marketers help identify the most in-demand products and develop strategies for their production. This may include seed selection and preparation, improved growing methods, and improved processing and preservation of produce.

Pricing: Marketing specialists help determine the optimal price for agricultural products, taking into account the competitive market situation, production costs, demand and other factors.

Product Promotion: Marketing activities include developing and implementing marketing strategies such as advertising, social media promotion and other activities aimed at attracting potential customers and increasing brand awareness.

Distribution: Marketers plan and organize the delivery and distribution of agricultural products to the market. They analyze logistics processes, select the most effective distribution channels and manage supply chains.

Customer Relationship Management: The marketing function involves maintaining and developing customer relationships, providing high levels of service, implementing after-sales services and obtaining customer feedback.

In general, agricultural marketing plays an important role in determining strategies for the production, promotion and sale of agricultural products in order to satisfy consumer needs and achieve successful results for agricultural enterprises.

He helps agricultural enterprises adapt to changing market conditions, build effective business models and create a competitive advantage. In addition, the marketing function makes it possible to ensure sustainable development of agriculture, improve the quality of products, increase their value and improve the standard of living of rural communities.

The marketing function in agriculture also plays an important role in promoting sustainable development, environmental sustainability and social responsibility. For example, marketing strategies may include promoting organic products, sustainable production methods, and a commitment to minimal use of chemicals. This helps maintain soil fertility, preserve biodiversity and improve environmental quality.

In this regard, marketing in agriculture is becoming an integral component of the successful activities of agricultural enterprises. To be competitive and successful in the market, it is necessary to pay due attention to marketing aspects, understand the needs of the market, develop products based on consumer requirements, effectively market and distribute your products, and establish and maintain relationships with customers.

Yes, agricultural marketing research is an important tool that allows you to analyze and understand the needs and preferences of consumers, determine strategies for promoting and selling agricultural products, and also predict demand and competition in the market. Marketing research helps agricultural businesses optimize their activities, improve the quality and pricing of their products, and develop marketing strategies to attract new customers and retain existing ones.

One of the main marketing strategies in agriculture in Uzbekistan until 2030 may be the development of the agricultural sector based on innovative technologies. This may include the following measures:

1. Introduction of modern technologies and methods of soil cultivation, fertilization, irrigation and plant protection, which will increase productivity and product quality.

2. Development of infrastructure and logistics for efficient transportation and storage of agricultural products, in order to minimize losses and optimize delivery to the end consumer.
3. Creation of a certification and labeling system for agricultural products to guarantee their quality and safety for the consumer.
4. Active promotion and marketing of Uzbek agricultural products in foreign markets, through participation in international exhibitions and conducting marketing research on the needs of potential foreign buyers.
5. Support and development of agro-tourism, as a new direction of agricultural development, in order to attract tourists and increase interest in Uzbek agricultural products.
6. Active use of information and communication technologies in the promotion and marketing of agricultural products, including the creation of electronic platforms for the sale and exchange of information between producers and consumers.
7. Development and support of small and medium-sized enterprises in agriculture to stimulate competition and diversity of products offered.
8. Conducting educational and information campaigns for rural residents and agricultural producers about the advantages and opportunities of modern marketing and effective management of agribusiness.

MAIN TARGETS AND INDICATORS,

achieved as a result of the implementation of the Agricultural Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020 - 2030

№	Names of indicators	Foundation (2018)	Goal for 2021	Goal for 2025	Goal for 2030
1.	Annual increase in value added in agriculture	117,3 trillion soums (\$14 billion)	3 %	5 %	5 %

2.	Job growth in the agri-food sector:				
	Agriculture	3 671 300	2 %	1 %	1 %
	food industry	91 420	3 %	4 %	5 %
	textile industry	140 200	3 %	4 %	3 %
3.	Increasing the volume of exports of agri-food products	US\$2.3 billion	US\$2.5 billion	\$10 billion	\$20 billion
4.	Proportion of population experiencing food insecurity	6,3 %	5 %	3 %	0
5.	Labor productivity in agriculture (per worker per year, US dollars)	3 960 US dollars	4 300 US dollars	5 200 US dollars	6 500 US dollars
6.	Reducing agricultural greenhouse gas emissions	15,740 gigagrams (2016 г.)	10 %	30 %	50 %

These strategies can contribute to the sustainable development of agriculture in Uzbekistan and increase its competitiveness in international markets in the period up to 2030.

References

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